

VIRTUAL SPACE AND ITS IMPACT ON THE PERSONALITY OF THE PEDAGOGUE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the psychological and pedagogical impact of virtual space on the personality of the modern pedagogue. The growing virtualization of society, driven by global technological development, has considerably transformed educational environments and professional requirements for teachers. Based on a review of scientific literature, the study analyzes psychological factors such as motivation, emotional state, personal qualities, and reflection, as well as pedagogical factors including national, moral, and ethical upbringing, information consumption culture, and deontological preparedness. The article argues that the development of virtual-pedagogical culture is essential for ensuring teachers' spiritual maturity, value orientation, and responsible interaction within the virtual environment. It also highlights four domains—individual, social, natural, and noospheric—in which a pedagogue must define their spiritual position. The findings emphasize the importance of integrating universal values, democratic principles, digital literacy, and ethical responsibility into the process of professional pedagogical development.

The processes of virtualization in society develop in parallel and in close connection with the processes of globalization. Examples such as virtual economy, virtual currency, virtual products, and others indicate the growing significance of virtual technologies in recent years. The main goal of virtual education, as well as the overall process of human upbringing, is to enable a person to define their destiny in the real world, including its virtual components, and to achieve it.

The term “*virtual*” originates from the Latin word “*vir*”, meaning “man.” The Romans derived the word “*virtus*” from it, signifying “brave, strong, courageous,” and referring to moral and behavioral virtues manifested by an individual. In Roman mythology, the goddess *Virtus* was characterized by these same attributes.

In the 12th century, the word entered French and later English. In science and technology, the concept of “*virtual reality*” was introduced in the late 1970s by Massachusetts Institute of Technology researcher Jaron Lanier, expressing the idea of a person's presence in a computer-generated environment.

During the analysis of literature, psychological factors were examined in connection with intellectual, emotional, and motivational domains. In the development of virtual-pedagogical culture in education, the roles of motivation, goals, emotions, personal qualities, and reflection were studied. Pedagogical factors included national, religious, and moral upbringing, educational paradigms, information consumption culture, and deontological preparedness.

The development of virtual-pedagogical culture requires improvement through a system of spiritual prevention, socio-pedagogical activity, and the integration of spiritual culture with education. As a pressing issue, spiritual culture manifests itself in four important domains in which pedagogues must determine their position (or acquire spiritual culture): the human being, society, nature, and the noosphere.

- **Defining one's place as a human being** requires understanding life, individuality as a value, and the human being as the peak of development.

- **Defining one's place in society** emerges through the adoption of values such as homeland, democracy, rule of law, family, labor, and civic responsibility.

- **Defining one's place in nature** involves understanding oneself as part of nature and improving oneself accordingly (health, aesthetics, spiritual and moral ideals). It also implies possessing ecological culture and recognizing responsibility toward future generations in the process of using and preserving nature.

- **Defining one's place in the noosphere (the realm of intellect)** requires understanding ethical responsibility in using scientific and technological achievements, recognizing the consequences of insufficient knowledge when interacting with technology, strengthening civic responsibility toward the historical, spiritual, and moral identity of the nation, preserving cultural heritage, restoring traditions, and revitalizing national customs.

Understanding virtual-pedagogical culture as the unity of these integrative domains allows us to view it as pedagogical activity aimed at creating psychological and pedagogical conditions to meet the basic needs of the individual. Such pedagogical conditions within the educational system include:

- diverse approaches to determining the content of education,
- dialogic, virtual, and discussion-based methods of upbringing,
- orientation toward universal human values in the personality formation process,
- the principles of democratization and consideration of national identity in organizing the educational process.

In today's rapidly developing information era, the culture of selecting and accurately evaluating information (virtual culture) in mass media is one of the most pressing issues. In the educational process, we believe that every specialist must first possess virtual-pedagogical culture in order to effectively address these challenges.

References:

1. Mo'minov, Elyor Abdualiyevich. Ta'lim tizimining virtuallashuvi – ilmiy samaradorlikni oshirish omili sifatida virtual ta'limni qo'llash. In: Fan va innovatsiya 2022: rivojlanish va ustuvor yo'nalishlari, Republican Scientific-Practical Conference Materials. Namangan, October 20, 2022.

2.Sayitova, U. (2025). Virtual ta'limda pedagog shaxsning shakllanishi. Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi jurnali, 3(4).

3.Sayitova, U. (2025). Pedagog kompetensiyasining turlari. Modern Science and Research, 4(2), 1414–1416.

